

Reflections on the Size of Chelate Rings

JOHN C. BAILAR, JR.

University of Illinois, Urbana, Illinois 61801, U.S.A.

It is fitting that we should commemorate the birthday of Professor Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, for he made great contributions to chemistry in India, and thus, to chemistry world-wide. His work in the early days of the Indian Chemical Society is especially noteworthy, as it did much to put that organisation on the solid foundation upon which it still rests. He will long be remembered.

In this paper, I propose to review the subject of chelate rings starting with the smallest and going to larger and larger rings. Three-membered rings have been postulated for complexes of sulphur dioxide¹ and the peroxy groups^{2,3}. There is clear evidence that in the SO₂ complexes, the sulphur atom and one oxygen atom are approximately equidistant from the metal to which the sulphur dioxide is coordinated, but the possibility remains that this 'side-on' binding is through the electrons in the S–O bond rather than through the individual atoms. The same is true of the peroxy complexes. Stromberg³ showed, twenty-five years ago, that the peroxy oxygen atoms in [CrO(O₂)₂ pyridine] are equidistant from the chromium atom, and drawings of the molecule show both peroxy oxygens linked to the chromium atom. However, these two oxygen atoms are very close together, so that if there is a three-membered ring, it must be highly strained. More recent papers⁴ are subject to the same uncertainty.

Four-membered chelate rings are not numerous, but are well-known. Carbonato complexes such as [Co(NH₃)₄CO₃]⁺ and [Co en₂CO₃]⁺ have long been known. Shibata and coworkers⁵ have developed an elegant synthetic method for the preparation of cobalt(III) complexes based on the stepwise replacement of the carbonato groups in Na₃[Co(CO₃)₃]. This has yielded such compounds as the purely inorganic chiral ions *cis-cis-cis*-[Co(NH₃)₂(H₂O)₂(CN)₂]⁺ and *cis-cis-cis*-[Co(NH₃)₂(H₂O)₂(NO₂)₂]⁺⁶. The carbonato group, as well as the nitrate and acetato groups, form four-membered rings with ions of the very heavy metals. Examples are Na₆[Th(CO₃)₃].12H₂O⁶, Na₆[Ce(CO₃)₃].12H₂O⁷, K₂[Er(NO₃)₂] (Ref. 8) and [UO₂Ac₂]⁻ (Ref. 9). The sulphato group can also form four-membered chelate rings, but it often coordinates through only one oxygen atom. Hertenberg and Bailar¹⁰ prepared a series of compounds containing the ion *cis*-[Co(NH₃)₄(H₂O)(SO₄)]⁺ and heated them. They found that if the anion is a good coordinator, e.g. Cl⁻, it enters the coordination sphere as the water leaves; thus the SO₄ group remains as a unidentate group. However, if the anion is a poor coordinator, e.g. ClO₄⁻, the sulphato group becomes bidentate. They also

showed¹¹ that the diaquo complex *cis*-[Co(NH₃)₄(H₂O)₂](SO₄)₂.3H₂O, upon dehydration, gives the dinuclear compound *cis-cis*-[SO₄(NH₃)₄CoSO₄Co(NH₃)₄SO₄] in which all three of the sulphato groups are unidentate, one of them serving as a bridge between the two cobalt atoms. Other important compounds containing four-membered rings are the two chiral compounds^{12,13},

Most of the four-membered rings thus contain oxygen as the donor atom. There are no ligands such as NH₂CH₂NH₂, NH₂COOH, or NH₂CH₂OH; such potential ligands have not been prepared.

Five-membered rings are, of course, very common, being formed by ethylenediamine, propylenediamine (1,2-diaminopropane), oxalate ion, glycinate ion, and many more. The chemical literature contains thousands of articles on five-membered chelate rings. Many of these concern isomerism of complexes: *cis-trans*, *dextro-levo*, *fac-mer*, and others. In general, five-membered rings are puckered, so the carbon-carbon bonds can lie nearly parallel to the C-axis of the complex (lel) and at a large angle from it (ob). If the chelate ring contains a substituent, as does propylenediamine, this substituent will tend to assume an axial position¹⁴. These properties severely limit the number of stereoisomers that form. For example, the complex [Copr₅]³⁺ theoretically can exist in sixteen stereoisomeric forms, not including the isomerism due to the chirality about the nitrogen atoms: Dddd (mer and fac), Dddl (mer and fac), Ddll (mer and fac), Dlll (mer and fac), Llld (mer and fac), Lldd (mer and fac), Lddd (mer and fac). However, only a few of these are usually isolated, for they differ in stability. The more stable forms are Dddd and Llll, but by very careful work, Dwyer and coworkers¹⁵ were able to isolate small quantities of the Dlll and Lddd isomers, and, by measuring the relative amounts of these, to calculate the relative stabilities of the

isomers. Their results and those of Corey and Bailar¹⁴, which were based on conformational analysis, agree well.

There are many complexes containing fused five-membered rings. These also show many types of isomerism. Thus two molecules of $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$ can form octahedral complexes which are either meridional or facial and $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$ (teten), with two unidentate groups, can form *trans*, α -*cis* and β -*cis* isomers. One complex, reported by Goedken and Christoph¹⁶ deserves special mention,

This molecule is a trigonal bipyramid, but it is badly distorted and is 'decidedly helical', so it is chiral.

Six-membered rings are not as common as five-membered ones, but a great many are known and are quite stable. Diamines such as trimethylenediamine ($\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$), β -amino acids and many other types of organic molecules give six-membered rings which are reasonably stable, but not as stable as those containing five-membered rings, as illustrated in Table 1, in which the logarithms of the approximate first stability constants are shown¹⁷.

TABLE 1

Ligand	Ring size	Od ¹⁷	Cu ¹⁷	Ni ¹⁷
$\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	5	5.5	10.7	7.7
$\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	6	5	9.8	6.7

Frequently, but not always, six-membered rings contain double bonds. Among such are the metal-dioxime complexes used in the analysis of nickel(II) and the compounds formed by β -diketones. Both the types of complexes are non-ionic, which perhaps enhances their stability. Some of the β -diketone complexes are volatile. This property is greatly enhanced in the complexes of the hexafluoro-diketones,

Sievers and coworkers¹⁸ were able to resolve this complex into its optically active forms by passing the vapours through a column of d-quartz powder at 55°.

Sargeson's 'sepulchrate' ions¹⁹ is remarkable in containing three fused six-membered rings at each end of the structure. These are formed by building onto the faces of the $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ octahedron that contain only nitrogen atoms. The complex is first treated with formaldehyde which puts a $=\text{CH}_2$ group on each nitrogen atom. This, in turn, is treated with ammonia, which reacts with three $=\text{CH}_2$ groups to close the rings.

Seven-membered rings are not common, partly because the necessary chelating agents are not readily available, but also because most such rings are inherently unstable. For example, the logarithm of the first stability constant of $[\text{Cd}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ is only 3.6¹⁷. This is not to say, however, that stable seven-membered rings do not exist, for, indeed, they do. Both 2,2'-dihydroxybiphenyl²⁰ and, 2,2'-diaminobiphenyl form stable complexes. A platinum(II) compound of this latter, $[\text{Pt en dabp}]^{2+}$, was prepared and resolved into its optical antipodes by Habu and Bailar²¹ and the cobalt complex $[\text{Co en}_2 \text{dabp}]^{2+}$ was resolved into its four optical isomers by McCollough and Bailar²². Both of these compounds proved to be quite stable toward racemisation. Stability is gained in these biphenylamine complexes by the fact that the phenyl groups can rotate about their common axis to relieve any undue strain.

Rings of eight-members or more are well established. In some cases, at least, they span the *trans*-positions in a planar complex, and in one case, an octahedral complex. Mattern, Mochida and Bailar²³ prepared a *trans*-spanned platinum(II) complex by treating *trans*- $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ with

Upon reduction of the platinum to the planar +2 state, the coordinated chlorine and the tertiary nitrogen (which was *trans* to it) were liberated from the platinum, forming an eight-membered ring.

Isslieb and Hohlfield²⁴ also had an eight-membered ring spanning the *trans*-positions in a planar nickel(II) complex. They prepared the nickel complexes of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11})_2\text{P}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{P}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11})_2$. With $n=3$ or 5, red diamagnetic complexes were obtained. With $n=3$, the complex had a dipole moment of 11.13 D, but when $n=5$, the dipole moment was only 2.37 D. Clearly, both the complexes were planar, but the one in which $n=5$ must have contained a *trans*-spanning ligand.

Still larger rings have been described. Nonayama and Nonayama²⁵ prepared a series of palladium(II) complexes of cyclic triamines,

With $n=5$, only two of the nitrogen atoms coordinated to the metals, but with $n=6, 7, 8$ or 10 , all three attached themselves. Another example is furnished by the work of Venanzi and coworkers²⁶. They prepared the large, rigid ligand,

and from it, the complexes with nickel(II), palladium(II) and platinum(II). These contained twelve-membered rings. The platinum complex was shown by nmr to be *trans*-spanned. A thirteen-membered ring was prepared by Schlesinger²⁷ who used bis-amino acids of the type,

as ligands. He reported that with $n=2$ or 3 , the copper complexes were blue, but when $n=10$, they were violet; with $n=7$, either form could be obtained. This was probably the first example of a *trans*-spanning ligand.

Ogino and Fujita²⁸ treated $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}$ with $\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{NH}_2$ in dimethylsulphoxide. When n was $4, 10, 12$ or 14 , they obtained chelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4 \text{ diamine}]^{2+}$ ion in which the organic amine formed rings of $7, 13, 15$ or 17 members, respectively. However, when n was $5, 6, 8$, no chelate rings were formed, but instead, dimeric species $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co diamine Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{4+}$. When n was 4 or 10 , both types of compounds were obtained. This use of DMSO may prove to be of great value in synthetic work. As the authors pointed out, their results are compatible with the instability of medium sized organic rings.

Finally, mention must be made of a remarkable ruthenium complex in which a ligand spans *trans*-positions in an octahedron²⁹, forming a twentyone membered ring,

It would seem from this that almost any size of large ring might be formed if the conditions are right.

References

1. R. R. RYAN, G. J. KUBAS, D. C. MOODY and P. G. ELLER, *Struct. Bonding*, 1981, **46**, 47, and references therein.
2. R. STROMBERG, *Ark. Kemi*, 1964, **22**, 29
3. M. K. CHAUDHURI and S. K. GHOSH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 534, E. M. NOUR, A. B. EL-SAYED and S. A. SADEK, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 317
4. M. MORI, M. SHIBATA, E. KYUNO and T. ADACHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1956, **29**, 883
5. S. SHIMBA, S. FUJINAMI and M. SHIBATA, *Chem. Lett.*, 1979, 783
6. S. VOLIOTIS and A. RIMSKY, *Acta Crystallogr., Part B*, 1975, **31**, 2615
7. S. VOLIOTIS and A. RIMSKY, *Acta Crystallogr., Part B*, 1975, **31**, 2620.
8. W. SCHWARTZ and H. J. GUDER, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1978, **444**, 105.
9. W. H. ZACHARIASEN and H. A. PLATTINGER, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1959, **12**, 526
10. E. P. HERTZENBERG and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2377
11. E. P. HERTZENBERG and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2371.
12. A. WERNER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 3087.
13. F. G. MANN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 412.
14. E. J. CORRY and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 2620.
15. F. P. DWYER, F. L. GARVAN and A. SCHULMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 290.
16. V. L. GOEDKEN and G. G. CHRISTOPH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **12**, 2316.
17. "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", Compiled A. E. MARTELL, Special Publication 17, The Chemical Society, London, 1964
18. R. E. SIEVERS, R. W. MOSHIER and M. L. MORRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 966, R. E. SIEVERS, B. W. PONDER, M. L. MORRIS and R. W. MOSHIER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 698, R. W. MOSHIER and R. E. SIEVERS, "Gas Chromatography of Metal Chelates", Pergamon, Oxford, 1965, p. 126.
19. A. M. SARGSON, *Chem. Br.*, 1979, **15**, 23.
20. K. ANDRÄ and HORST-RUEDIGER HOPPE, *Z. Chem.*, 1980, **20**, 267
21. T. HABU and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1128.

22. F. McCOLLOUGH, Jr. and J. C. BAILAR, Jr., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 714.
23. J. A. MATTERN, Ph.D Thesis, University of Illinois, 1946 ; I. MOCHIDA, J. A. MATTERN and J. C. BAILAR, Jr., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 3021.
24. K. ISSLIEB and G. HOHLFELD, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1962, **312**, 169.
25. M. NONAYAMA and K. NONAYAMA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **35**, 231.
26. N. J. DESTEPHANO, D. K. JOHNSON and L. M. VENANZI, *Angew. Chem.*, 1974, **86**, 133 ; (*Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1974, **13**, 133).
27. N. SCHLESINGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1925, **58**, 1877.
28. H. OGINO and J. FUJITA, *Chem. Lett.*, 1973, 517, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, **48**, 1836 ; H. OGINO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1977, **50**, 2459.
29. R. A. LEISING, J. J. GRZYBOWSKI and K. J. TAKEUCHI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 1020.